

Synthesis and Evaluation of Thermodynamic Functions for Complexation Reactions involving Bivalent Metal Ions and Di(2-ethylphenyl)carbazone

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The nuclear substituted derivatives of diphenylcarbazone (DPC) give intense colouration with many metal ions suggesting their possible use as analytical reagents. In continuation of our studies on the synthesis and complexing abilities of the nuclear substituted derivatives of diphenylcarbazone¹ and keeping in view of their applications, we report here the synthesis and studies on di(2-ethylphenyl)carbazone (DOEPC).

Results and Discussion

The formation curve of DOEPC is found to be a single wave extending from 0 to 1 and the slope of the plot of $\log \bar{n}_A/(1-\bar{n}_A)$ vs pH is 0.96; both indicate the monobasic nature of DOEPC. The pK_a value of DOEPC is 9.97 at 25°, which is higher than that of DPC (9.26); this is expected due to the substitution of electron-donating C_2H_5 group in the *ortho*-position. The acid dissociation constants (pK_a) and stability constants have been found to decrease with increasing temperature of the medium (Table 1).

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF BIVALENT METAL COMPLEXES OF DI(2-ETHYLPHENYL)CARBAZONE (DOEPC) AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

$\mu = 0.1 M (NaClO_4)$, medium 50% (v/v) dioxan-water

System	Stability constants	Weighted least-squares method		
		25°	35°	45°
DOEPC	pK_a	9.97	9.86	9.82
Cu ^{II} -DOEPC	$\log K_1$	8.60	8.52	8.36
	$\log K_2$	8.25	8.01	7.71
Ni ^{II} -DOEPC	$\log K_1$	5.76	5.60	5.51
	$\log K_2$	5.16	5.10	4.92
Zn ^{II} -DOEPC	$\log K_1$	6.02	5.80	5.65
	$\log K_2$	5.35	5.20	5.08
Co ^{II} -DOEPC	$\log K_1$	5.26	—	—
	$\log K_2$	4.83	—	—
Cd ^{II} -DOEPC	$\log K_1$	4.67	—	—
	$\log K_2$	4.30	—	—
Mn ^{II} -DOEPC	$\log K_1$	4.18	—	—
	$\log K_2$	3.66	—	—

It has been shown that the complex formation takes place between the \bar{O} and $-N<$ of the ligand and the metal ions¹⁻³. The results summarise the formation constants of metal DOEPC systems at 25° and in some cases also at 35 and 45°. The order of formation constants is as follows: Cu^{II} > Zn^{II} > Ni^{II} > Co^{II} > Cd^{II} > Mn^{II}. The fact that Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} form very very weak complexes, they are

not reported here. This order is in good agreement with the order as determined by Irving and Williams^{4,5} and Mellor and Maley⁶. The additional high stability of the Cu^{II} complex is attributed to the unsymmetrical electronic configuration ($3d^9$) of Cu^{II} ion which is capable of additional stabilisation due to Jahn-Teller distortion. Similar conclusions were also drawn by Gaber *et al.*⁷ in explaining the high stability of Cu^{II} complexes of salicylic acid derivatives.

In general, $\log K_1 > \log K_2$ for a given metal ion; however, the difference in the values between the two constants is not much, indicating that there is almost an equal tendency for the formation of neutral complex species. In fact, the maximum \bar{n} value observed in the present experiments is ~2.0, which supports our assumption of 1 : 2 stoichiometry. In view of the fact that very low concentrations of metal ions have been used in the titrations, the possibility of formation of polynuclear complexes is negligible.

The estimated thermodynamic parameters (Table 2) show that the change of standard free energy (ΔG°) is negative indicating that complex formation reactions are spontaneous. The negative ΔH° values indicate the exothermic nature of the complexation reactions. In so far as ΔH° is a measure of the strength of the covalent bonding, it is concluded that the Cu^{II} complexes are more strongly bound than the Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes. Large value of ΔH° associated with Cu^{II} indicates the high covalent character. In all the cases, ΔS° values are positive, showing that the complexation processes are thermodynamically favourable.

TABLE-2 THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF BIVALENT METAL COMPLEXES WITH DI(2-ETHYLPHENYL)CARBAZONE

Temp = 25 ± 0.1°, $\mu = 0.1 M (NaClO_4)$

Metal ion	$-\Delta G^\circ$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta H^\circ$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\circ$ e u
Cu ^{II}	11.7	5.2	21.9
Ni ^{II}	7.9	4.5	11.3
Zn ^{II}	8.2	0.9	24.5

Experimental

¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) were recorded on a Varian XL(300 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal reference, electron-impact mass spectra on an AEI MS30 instrument equipped with an MSS system and ir spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 1430 spectrophotometer. A Systronics 335

pH-meter with glass and saturated calomel electrodes assembly was used and standardised with potassium hydrogen phthalate and phosphate buffers before performing titrations.

2-Ethylphenylhydrazine hydrochloride⁸ (1) dissolved in hot water was treated with NaOH solution (10%) maintaining the temperature below 15°. The resulting pale yellow hydrazine was extracted with diethyl ether. The ether extract was washed with water, dried (Na₂SO₄) and concentrated to yield crystals of 2-ethylphenylhydrazine and dried under reduced pressure over P₂O₅ for 12 h, m.p. 28°.

Di(2-ethylphenyl)carbazine (2) : Compound 1 (0.08 mol) was heated with urea (0.04 mol) in an oil-bath at 140–55° for 3 h and cooled. The resulting solid was crystallised from alcohol and dried under reduced pressure (75–80 mm), m.p. 142° (Found : C, 68.38; H, 7.39; N, 18.75. C₁₇H₂₂N₄O requires : C, 68.43; H, 7.43; N, 18.79%).

Di(2-ethylphenyl)carbazone (3) : Compound 2 (0.013 mol) dissolved in glacial acetic acid (240 ml) was diluted with 1 N H₂SO₄ (80 ml) and 2-drops of ferric alum (10%) was added. Then a solution of potassium persulphate (0.018 mol) in water (80 ml) was added dropwise with vigorous stirring, allowed to stand for 30 min, diluted with ice-cold water and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with distilled water till it was free from acetic acid. On evaporation of ether the resulting product was chromatographed over SiO₂ (60–120 mesh), eluted with acetone-chloroform mixture (20 : 80) and evaporation of the eluent gave pale yellow crystals of 3 (40–45%), m.p. 65–66° (Found : C, 68.62; H, 6.60; N, 18.28. C₁₇H₂₀N₄O requires : C, 68.89; H, 6.80; N, 18.91%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 350, 3 100, 2 900, 1 725, 1 700, 1 587, 1 475 and 775 cm⁻¹; δ 1.3 (6H, t, CH₃), 2.83 (4H, q, CH₂), 6.8–7.4 (8H, m, ArH), 8.9 (1H, s, NH) and 11.5 (s, OH); m/z 296 (M⁺).

On the basis of the above analysis and spectral study, structures (I) and (II) may be assigned to DOEPC 3 (Chart 1). The sites of coordination are shown by the asterisks on the nitrogen and oxygen atoms in (II).

Chart 1

The solution of the ligand was prepared in dioxan. All the metal ion solutions were prepared from their corresponding sulphates or nitrates (AnalaR) in double-distilled water and standardised by EDTA method⁹. Sodium perchlorate (Riedel) was used to maintain constant ionic strength. Double-distilled water and carbonate-free NaOH solution were prepared¹⁰. Dioxan (A.R.) was purified¹¹. A solution of NaOH was used as the titrant and standardised with potassium hydrogen phthalate. The titrations were carried out in an inert N₂-atmosphere presaturated with 50%

(v/v) aqueous dioxan before passing through the reaction mixture.

The method of Calvin-Bjerrum as modified by Irving and Rossotti¹² was followed to determine the proton-ligand and metal ligand stability constants.

The following sets of titrations were performed at three different temperatures, 25, 35 and 45 ± 0.1° in 50% dioxan-water medium : (i) 5 ml HClO₄ (0.1 M) + 5 ml NaClO₄ (1.0 M) + 25 ml dioxan + 15 ml H₂O, (ii) 5 ml HClO₄ (0.1 M) + 5 ml NaClO₄ (1.0 M) + 5 ml ligand (2.0 × 10⁻² M) + 20 ml dioxan + 15 ml H₂O, (iii) 5 ml HClO₄ (0.1 M) + 5 ml NaClO₄ (1.0 M) + 5 ml ligand (2.0 × 10⁻² M) + 5 ml metal ion solution (5 × 10⁻³ M) + 20 ml dioxan + 10 ml H₂O. Total volume in each case was 50 ml and ionic strength was maintained constant at 0.1 M (NaClO₄). The ratio of the metal salt to reagent was maintained at nearly 1 : 4 in all the titrations in order to satisfy the maximum coordination possibility of the metal ions.

In all the calculations, pH correction and volume correction factors were applied for dioxan-water mixture. From the titration curves of solutions (i), (ii) and (iii), the values of \bar{n} and pL were calculated using a PC-XT computer. The corresponding values of stability constants were calculated using weighted least-squares method¹³. The weighted least-squares treatment determined the set of β_n values which make the function U ,

$$U = \sum_{n=0}^N (y - x - nz) \beta_n \chi^n$$

nearest to zero, by minimising S ,

$$S = \sum_{i=1}^I W_i U^2(x_i, y_i, z_i)$$

with respect to variation in β_n . S_{\min} has the same statistical distribution as χ^2 with K degrees of freedom and the weights defined in accordance with Rydberg and Sullivan¹⁴. S_{\min} can be equated to χ^2 . The stability constants thus calculated are given in Table 1. The ΔH was calculated by the graphical method¹⁵ while ΔG and ΔS were calculated by conventional methods (Table 2).

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